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INTEGRITY AND PROFESSIONALISM OF THE GENERAL ELECTION COMMISSION IN NORTH MALUKU PROVINCE AT PRESIDENTIAL ELECTION IN INDONESIA 2014

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the perceptions and expectations of the people associated with the integrity and professionalism of the organizers of the election in the 2014 presidential election in the 4th District / City of North Maluku province, as well as provide a thorough assessment of the quality of the 2014 presidential election as an input and improvements in looking to the upcoming 2019 Presidential Election. This study uses a survey, taking a sample of 400 respondents in four Regency / City (East Halmahera, South Halmahera regency, Central Halmahera and Ternate). Sampling using purposive sampling method that is based on the number of residents and representatives of community characteristics based on race / ethnicity, highest level of violation. These results indicate that 30 percent of respondents doubt the integrity and professionalism of the Operator Pilpres both KPU and Regency / City and KDP (district level) and PPS (village) relating to the stages of the determination of vote counts, the implementation of the recapitulation of vote counting, procurement logistics and distribution of ballot papers, exercising campaign, socialization, and update the data of voters (DPT). Likewise still lack of integrity and professionalism Bawaslu North Maluku Province, Supervisory District / Town, District and Village / Lurah. 30percent of respondents said surveillance of the stages of the Presidential Election as the duty of the Provincial Election Supervisory Body doubt the integrity and professionalism. Similarly DKPP (Honorary Council Election) still weak in resolving cases of violation of the code of conduct organizers. It was concluded that the weak responsiveness of the organizers of the Provincial KPU, Bawaslu Province and DKPP in the running phases of election of the President and Vice President of integrity and professionalism. Step improvement course conducted political education in reducing the number Abstentions (Voter Turnout), improved management of the electoral system, reform data update, change the public's distrust of the organizers of the way the practice of transparency and accountability of the providers through dialogue, reports and audit election fund.

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INTRODUCTION

Evaluation of the 2014 Indonesian presidential election earlier, needs to be done. This evaluation aims to refit the whole process of implementation of the Presidential Election technically qualified in the days that will come. In the 2014 presidential election, there are still many problems associated with the guarantee of the election organizers in setting up a distribution system through the presidential aspirations of the people throughout the region. In other words, weak collateral

channeling the aspirations of the people through the 2014 presidential election will weaken public confidence in the organizers, demoting a procedural democracy, and not the strengthening of popular legitimacy of the candidates for President and Vice President. This research was focused on the evaluation of the Integrity and Professionalism Election in 2014 presidential. Particularly with respect to the ability of the election organizer to act professionally and implement the principle of elections within the framework of the code of conduct, as well as capability of human resources and capabilities election organizers in running the technical implementation of the 2014 presidential election. Meanwhile, in terms of substance, the analysis is intended to analyze the

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internal dynamics of the organizers, various activities in carrying out the stages of the 2014 presidential election. The study is expected to provide objective input materials from the region in the form of recommendations and improvement of the implementation of the Presidential election in the future, especially in carrying out simultaneous legislative elections and the 2019 Presidential election. Some facts show that if the election organizer mainly general election commissions (KPU) can be trusted by voters as the election organizer; breaches of the code of conduct or malpractice committed, alignments election organizers on valid candidate, How transparency of the management of the election, the accuracy of registration / update voter data. Many of the residents who lost their voting rights because it is not registered in the voters list (DPT), regulation of campaign and level of violations occurred and how the process of electoral justice was done by Bawasluand KPU of calculation and tabulation of the transparent and accurate data, the validity and reliability was consistent. The success and failure of election lies in the integrity and readiness professionalism election itself, namely the Election Commission, the Elections Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu), and Honorary Board of Election (DKPP) as an integral function of the administration of elections. These three institutions have been mandated by legislation to hold elections according to the functions, duties and authority of each. Various problems often found in the Presidential Election Commission as organizers stage, among others, the *First*, the stages of voter data appeared several crucial issues that the DPS was not announced, Problems DPT, Money Politics, Campaigns outside the schedule. *Second*, at this stage of the nomination of the Commission is often different understanding in interpreting candidates who meet or do not meet the provisions of candidacy administrative requirements, incompatibility adannya registration files given to the Commission would be candidates, forgery of signatures of support campaigns beyond the schedule Transitional party support. Third, in the stages of the campaign often creates several offenses, among others: Installation of props that are not according to the rules, campaigns outside the schedule, location change campaign without notification to the Commission, involvement of minors, Political Money, destruction of campaign attributes, the use of facilities Country , involvement of civil servants, Black Campaign. Fourth, the stages of voting and counting raises some issues, such as the photo division of invitation letters to registered voters, presence of people who cast by using an invitation card or another person's name, still finding eligible voters who are not enrolled in DPT, Displacement of polling locations, BA or certificate calculation does not exist in the ballot box, Political Money, voted more than once, the involvement of the government to win, Intimidation of one candidate, Penggelumbungan and noise reduction, veiled campaign, the rights for voice and sound manipulation.

The issue became a limiting factor on the integrity and professionalism of the organizers of the election. At every stage of the election often cause offense lead to administrative and criminal. Thus, this study seeks to explore a wide range of opinion and public opinion, especially in some districts / municipalities vulnerable and Paing many violations of the election.

As we know that the recapitulation of the 2014 presidential election in North Maluku province Prabowo-Hatta obtained 306 792 votes (54.45percent). And Jokowi-JK: 256 601 votes (45.54percent). Tota 565 970 valid votes as much as the sound. While the permanent voters list (DPT) Presidential Election in North Maluku detailed as follows, Male 426 742 inhabitants, and the Women's 413 511 inhabitants with a total of 859 717 low voter participation can be seen in the difference between DPT and legitimate voice as many as 293 747 people (34percent) were not choose. That is, only about 66percent are using the right to vote.

Statement of the problem

Based on the description above background, the problems that occurred was lack of integrity and profesionaitas election organizers in the 2014 presidential election and required no fundamental evaluation of the performance of the integrity and professionalism of the organizers of the election in the District / City in the province of North Maluku.

Methodology

This study uses a survey approach. Survey takes a sample of the population and using questionnaires as the main data collection tool (Singarimbun and Effendi, 1989: 1). Survey research is quantitative research. The total sample consisted of 400 respondents from various circles that represent the entire number of voters in North Maluku province, especially in the districts / cities that were problematic during one month, with a margin of error of 5percent. Samples were taken by multi stage random sampling. Retrieving data using questionnaires for primary data and related documents as secondary data. Furthermore, the data were analyzed descriptively quantitive accordance with the objectives to be achieved.

Concept of Professionalim and Integrity

De George explained that the Professionals are people who have a profession or a full time job and live off the job by relying on a high craftsmanship. The professional is a person who lives by practicing a particular skill or to engage in certain activities according to expertise, spare time. Wolmer and Mills (Sardiman, 2007; 164), said That "work was regarded as a profession if it meets the following criteria: (1) Having a specialty with an extensive background; (2) It is a career that fostered organizationally; (3) Recognized community as having the status of a professional job". Natawijaya (2006) suggested several criteria as the hallmark of a profession that is: (1) There is a basic work standards and clear; 2. There is a special educational institution that produce the culprit with good educational programs; (3). There is adequate organization culprit to defend and fight for the existence and well-being; (4). There are ethics and codes of conduct governing the behavior of the actors in his clients; (5). There is a reward system that is fair to its services and raw. If it is associated with the concept of professionalism, in, Indonesian Dictionary (2001: 897) mentions a job must have a meaning such as quality, and behavior that is characteristic of a profession or a professional. Professionalism is an attitude of a professional. In other words, the professional becomes a

term of professionalism when every employment shall be done by a person skilled in the art or profession.

Sjafri Sairin (2003), the use of the term professionalism refers to the degree of a person's appearance or performance as professional a job as a profession, there is the professionalism of high, medium and low. Professionalism also refers to the attitude and commitment of the members of the profession to work based on a high standard and code of conduct of his profession. The concept of professionalism, as in the study developed by Hall in Sairin, the word is widely used research to see how the professionals looked at his profession, which is reflected in their attitudes and behavior. Sumardi (2001) explains that he has five principles, namely: *First*, the affiliate community (community affiliation) that is used as a reference professional associations, including the formal organization or informal groups of colleagues work main source of ideas. Through this professional associations professionals build awareness of the profession. *Second*, the need for independence (autonomy demand) is a professional say that a person should be able to make their own decisions without pressure from other parties (government, clients, those who are not members of the profession). Each of the intervention (intervention) coming from the outside, is regarded as an obstacle to the development of independent professional.

Siagian (2009: 163) professionalism is, "Reliability and expertise in performing the tasks so done with high quality, timely manner, accurately, and with procedures that are easily understood and followed by the customers." Sedarmayanti (2004: 157) revealed that " professionalism is an attitude or state in carrying out the work requires expertise through education and specific training and performed as a work that became a source of income. Atmosoeparto in Kurniawan (2005: 74), states that, "Professionalism is a reflection of the ability (competensi), which has the knowledge (knowledge), skills (skills), can do (ability) is supported by the experience (experience) that appears unlikely to arrive -Arrived without a journey through time. Dwiyanto (2011: 157) defines professionalism as "Understood or belief that the attitudes and actions of government officials in organizing activities and services are always based on science and the values of the profession personnel who put the interests of the public. Kurniawan (2005: 79) argues that the form of the ability to recognize the needs of the community, set an agenda, prioritize services, and develop service programs according to the needs and aspirations of the community or termed *responsivitas*. Sri Yuliani (2015) describes the Integrity or integrity is a concept that refers to the consistency between action by *Snilai* and principles. In ethics, integrity is defined as honesty and truth of one's actions. The opposite of integrity is *hipocrisy* (hypocrite or hypocritical). One is said to "have integrity" when its conduct in accordance with the values, beliefs, and principles held (Wikipedia). Integrity is the key character for a leader. A leader with integrity will gain confidence (trust) of the employees. Leaders of integrity believed because of what the words are also becoming actions. In connection with the work, then the Work Integrity is acting consistent with the policy and code of conduct an Institute. Having an understanding and a desire to conform to the policy and ethics, and act consistently although it is difficult to do so.

Rahman (2006) emphasize the significance integrity as an action that is consistent with the values and policies of the organization as well as the code of professional conduct, even in a state that is difficult to do this. In other words, "the only words with deeds". Communicating intentions, ideas and feelings in an open, honest and straightforward even in difficult negotiations with other parties. Behavior Indicators integrity can be expressed as follows: *First*, Understand and recognize the behavior according to the code of conduct. The real action that can be done include: (1) follow a code of professional conduct of the institution; (2) Be honest in using and managing resources within the scope or authority; (3) Take the time to make sure that what was done was not in violation of the code of conduct. *Second*, take action consistent with the values (values) and beliefs. Consistency of values that can be seen in aspects: (1) Perform the actions that are consistent with the values and beliefs; (2) Speaking lack of ethic though it will hurt a colleague or co-worker; (3) be honest in their dealings with other parties. *Third*, the Act based on the value (values) although it is difficult to do that. Things that should be done, among others, (1) openly admitted to having made a mistake; (2) frank although it can ruin a good relationship; (3) Acting on the value (values) although there is a risk or a considerable cost; (4) Be willing to back down or pull performance is unethical; (5) against those who have the power to uphold values.

The election code of conduct

In a joint regulation Election Commission, General Elections Supervisory Board, and the Honorary Council General Election Organizer No. 13 of 2012, No. 11 of 2012, No. 1 of 2012 on the Code of Conduct General Election Organizer explained that the Election is the means of implementation of the sovereignty of the people who organized direct, public, free, confidential, honest and fair in the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia in Year 1945. In connection with the presidential election, clearly stated that the President and Vice President are elections for President and Vice President democratically within the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia in Year 1945. Elections are held by the organizers of the election. Election organizers are institutions that hold elections which consists of the Election Commission and the Election Supervisory Agency (Bawaslu) as an integral function of the holding of elections to choose members of the House of Representatives, Regional Representatives Council, Regional Representatives Council, the President and the Vice President directly by the people, as well as to elect governors, regents and mayors democratically. In connection with the professional and integrity within the meaning of the Implementation of the Presidential and Vice-President of the Election, it presses on the regulatory function of the code of conduct of election organizer. The code of ethics is an integral foundation of moral norms, ethical and philosophical guidance for conduct of the general elections that are required, prohibited, or what is not worth doing in all actions and sayings. Adherence to the principle of elections, among others, to uphold the values of a. independently; b. honest; c. fair; d. legal certainty; e. orderly; f. public interest; g. openness; h.

proportionality; i. professionalism; j. accountability; k. efficiency; and l. effectiveness.

Liabilities Election

In maintaining the integrity and professionalism of institutional performance, the election organizer has the obligation under Article 7, namely; (A) Maintain and keep independence of Election Commission; (B) Running a task according to the vision, mission, goals, and programs of Election commission; (C) Keep the secret entrusted to him, including the results of the meeting, expressed as a secret until the time limit has been determined or until the issue has been declared to the public the extent not inconsistent with legislation; (D) Respect and honor fellow institutions and stakeholders Election Election; and (e) Make every effort is justified ethics is not contrary to legislation making it possible for each of the voting population registered as voters and be able to use their right to vote. Other obligations defined in Article 8 of the Election Code that shall: a. to keep and maintain social order in the administration of elections; b. heed the norms in the administration of elections; and c. respecting the diversity of Indonesian society. Similarly, in Article 9 emphasized that the Election shall: (a) faithful and devoted to God Almighty; (B) upholds the oath / pledge of office in carrying out the duties, powers, obligations and responsibilities; (C) keep and maintain neutrality, impartiality, and principles of election an honest, fair, and democratic; (D) did not include or involve kepen. Stingan individuals and families throughout the implementation of the duties, powers, and obligations; (D) performing the duties corresponding position and authority that is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, laws, regulations, and decisions related to the administration of elections; (E) to prevent all forms and types of abuse of duties, powers, and positions, either directly or indirectly; (F) refuses to accept money, goods and / or services or granting more when converted beyond the standard generalized cost within a period of three (3) hours, in certain activities directly or indirectly from potential participants Election, electoral participants, DPR and DPRD member candidates, and the campaign team; (G) prevent or prohibit the husband / wife, children, and individuals who have blood ties / related by marriage to the third degree, or the relationship of husband / wife divorced under the influence, guide, or the authorities concerned, to ask for or accept appointment, gifts , grants, gifts, awards, and loans or any of the parties concerned with the administration of elections; (H) expressed openly in a meeting if they have relatives or family relationship with the candidate, electoral participants, or the campaign team.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Characteristics of respondents in research on Integrity and Professionalism organizers Election of President and Vice President in 2014, especially in the province of North Maluku showed that the Respondents by ethnic Ternate as much as 27, and the least number of respondents is Sanana (1percent) and Java (2percent). While 17percent of respondents were from Tobelo Galela (Togale), 13percent of respondents were from Makian Kayoa (Makayoa), 13percent of respondents were from Bugis, Buton and Makassar (BBM), and 13percent of respondents were from Maba. Meanwhile, 6percent of

respondents were from Tidore, 4percent of respondents are from Jailolo and 4percent of respondents were from Patani.

Participation rate select respondents

Participation Rate respondents in choosing very high, as many as 390 or 98percent of respondents stated that they had participated in the 2014 presidential election as well as the last, and only 2percent of respondents who admitted to not exercise their right to vote in the 2014 presidential election (Figure 1). Respondents offered several fundamental reasons above do not use the right to vote in the 2014 presidential election Highest Score as much as 37.5percent had no preference for reasoned pemilih not listed in the list (DPT), followed by other reasons by 25percent, do not believe the organizers 12.5percent, 12.5percent bored and did not believe the candidates fielded by political parties amounted to 12.5percent (Figure 2). Nevertheless, the majority of respondents still give a positive perception that 40percent of respondents rate the Implementation of the 2014 presidential election is still integrity and professional, but this perception is also followed by the doubts of respondents to the implementation of the 2014 presidential election by 35percent. While 12percent of respondents considered the implementation of the 2014 presidential election and professional integrity. Similarly, 12percent of respondents also conversely assess the implementation of the 2014 presidential election it organized and professional integrity, and only 1percent are assessing the implementation of the presidential election in 2014 is not very integrity and professional (Figure 3).

The integrity of election organizer

Indicators are judged to be associated with the integrity of the election management including; act in a neutral and impartial justice to all couples, not to interfering with the other party, not to partisan, on hearing all the parties, and does not to accept giftin any form. Survey of the results showed that, on average the election supervisor agency (Bawaslu) North Maluku province is perceived by the public has a degree of professionalism better than the KPU of North Maluku Province in presidential election 2014. For the integrity of the degree of "good", 37percent perceived good Bawaslu, on four indicators, namely, "to be fair to each partner, not interfering with, not partisan, and listen to all interested parties. While on the other hand, the provincial KPU for the professionalism indicator only, 35percent for the three categories namely; not interfering with, not partisan and listen to all interested parties, and other indicators in the range of 30-33percent for the degree of "good". To the degree of integrity in the category of "less" public perception to Bawaslu still better when compared with the Commission or KPU. For example, for "intervention indicators", 18.3percent said they actually interfering with the Election Commission, while for Bawaslu intervesion degrees lower because only 10.5percent of respondents still perceive Bawaslu not to intervention. While indicators of the integrity of the other, the trend remains the same where Bawaslu still perceived better if compared to the Election Commission, for example on the indicator "justice to every partner", 17percent reesponden said that the Election Commission for the degree of fairness is considered less, but on the other hand only 9.7percent of respondents Bawaslu less to assess the degree of fairness (Figure 4).

Figure 1. Participation of Respondent

Figure 2. The reasons of abstain in presidential election 2014

Figure 3. Perception of organizing presidential elections 2014

Figure 4. Integrity Provincial KPU and Bawaslu North Maluku Province

Figure 5. Integrity comparison of regency election commission and regency Election Supervisory Committee

Figure 6. Integrity of districts election organizers

Figure 7. Professionalism of province election commission

Figure 8. Professionalism of regency election commission

Figure 9. Professionalism of district election commission

Table 1. Professionalism of election supervisory agency

Derajat Profesionalisme	Pemutahiran data pemilih tetap (DPT)	Melaksanakan sosialisasi	Pelaksanaan Kampanye	Pengadaan Logistik & distribusi	Pelaksanaan rekapitulasi hasil perhitungan suara	Penetapan Hasil
Bawaslu Provinsi						
Sangat Tidak Profesional	12.5	8	10.7	6	8.3	8.6
Tidak profesional	18	14.8	14.6	11.2	15.6	18.8
ragu-ragu	39.6	37.3	33.6	34.1	38	34.1
profesional	26.3	35.5	37.5	43.5	33.9	32.3
Sangat Profesional	3.6	4.4	3.6	5.2	4.2	6.2
Panwaslu Kabupaten						
Sangat Tidak Profesional	11.9	6.7	9.6	3.6	6	6.5
Tidak profesional	16.1	17.3	14	11.9	15.3	20.8
ragu-ragu	35.6	36.4	35.6	37.4	40	35.3
profesional	32.7	36.4	37.1	42.1	34	31.2
Sangat Profesional	3.6	2.8	3.6	4.9	4.7	6.2

Further, the integrity of the organizers in this case the Election Commission and the Election Supervisory Agency North Maluku province with the degree of perception of "very good" average on every indicator Bawaslu exceed the Election Commission. For example, for the indicator; "Act impartially, hearing all the parties, and not accept gifts of any kind" Bawaslu perceived in the range, 5percent "very good", the Election Commission on a range of 4percent "very good". In the degree of "very good" there is only one indicator of the integrity of the Election Commission which goes beyond Bawaslu namely on the indicator "justice to any couple" with the degree of 4.2percent to 3.4percent for the Election Commission and the Election Supervisory Agency or difference of 0.8percent (Figure 5). Integrity election organizers at the district level pattern is approximately equal to the provincial level, where the results of the survey addressed that average degree of integrity for all indicators, election supervisors tend to be better than the regency. To the degree the integrity of "good" indicator; "act in a neutral and impartial justice to all couples, not interfering with the other party, not partisan, on hearing all the parties, and does not accept gift in any form", the District Election Supervisory Committee has degrees respectively respectively, 32.8percent, 35.7percent, 37.4percent, 36percent, 36.5percent, 31.8percent, while the Regency degree respectively, 25.5percent, 28.3percent, 31.3percent, 34.2percent, 34.1percent, 28.8.

Difference degrees to the category of "good" on each indicator in the range of 2percent - 7percent. As for the degree with the assessment of "less", applies the reverse where Regency has a score higher percentage of District Election Supervisory Committee. For example, for the indicator, Acting impartially and justly in every pair ", the Regency perceived" lesser "respectively, 22percent and 22.3percent, while the District Election Supervisory Committee on the other hand only 13.6percent and 12.9percent with less votes. From these data address the perception that there is consistency with the previous assessment, in which respondents rate the county Election Commission has a larger shortfall for both these indicators when compared with the Election Supervisory Committee.

Further data related to the integrity of the organizers at the district level. In this level, we can see the comparison between the KDP and the Election Supervisory Committee integrity districts. For leve districts, KDP perceived integrity of "good", 33.1percent "independence", 36.3percent justice to every partner, 37.8percent not interference. Other hand, 39percent are not to partisan, 36.5percent listen to all sides, and 28.6percent not to accept any gift". While Panwaslu districts with integrity "good", "35.7percent" independence ", 41.3percent justice to every partner, 41.8percent did not independence, 40.6percent

are not partisan, 42.6percent listen to all sides, and 30.5percent did not receive gifts in any form " (Figure 6).

Professionalism of election organizer

When asked to 400 respondents about the professionalism of the Election Commission of North Maluku Province in organizing the presidential election, 7.8 percent or 31 people who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 20.8 percent or 83 respondents say unprofessional, 30.1 percent or 120 respondents said professional, 7.3 per cent or 29 respondents say it is very professional, while 34 percent, or 136 people / respondents undecided (Figure 7). The next question related to the implementation of the recapitulation, of the 400 respondents were interviewed about the professionalism of the Election Commission of North Maluku province in the implementation of the capitulation of the results, 7.5 percent or 30 people who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 20.8 percent or 83 respondents said unprofessional, 34.3 percent or 137 respondents said professional, 5.5 percent or 22 respondents say it is very professional, while 31.9 percent, or 128 people / respondents undecided. As for the question relating to the procurement of logistics and distribution of ballot papers, of the 400 respondents were interviewed about the professionalism of the Election Commission of North Maluku Province in procurement logistics and distribution of ballot papers, 5.2 percent or 21 people who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 21.8 percent or 66 respondents said unprofessional, 30.6 percent or 153 respondents said professional, 6.2 percent or 25 respondents say it is very professional, while 34 percent, or 136 people / respondents undecided. The next question related to the implementation of the campaign, of the 400 respondents interviewed 11.2 percent, or 45 people who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 16.4 per cent or 66 respondents say unprofessional, 38.2 percent or 153 respondents said professional, or 6.2 percent 25 respondents said it was very professional, while 34 percent, or 136 people / respondents undecided. The questions related to the socialization of the implementation of the presidential election, of the 400 respondents interviewed, 9.1 percent or 36 respondents who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 21.8 percent or 87 respondents say unprofessional, 30.6 percent or 122 respondents said professional, 4.1 percent or 16 respondents say it is very professional, while 34.5 percent, or 138 respondents undecided.

Likewise, questions relating to the updating of the voters' data, of the 400 respondents interviewed, 11.4 percent, or 46 respondents who said that the Election Commission of North Maluku Province is very unprofessional, 24.2 percent or 97 respondents said not a professional, 26 percent or 104 respondents said professional, 3.1 percent or 12 respondents say it is very professional, while 35.3 percent, or 141 respondents undecided (Figure 8). When asked to 400 respondents about the professionalism of the District Election Commission in organizing the presidential election, 4.7 percent, or 19 respondents, said district commissioner / City

very unprofessional, 25.8 percent or 103 respondents said unprofessional, 31.9 percent or 128 respondents said professional, 6 per cent or 24 respondents say it is very professional, while 31.6 percent, or 126 respondents undecided. The next question related to the implementation of the recapitulation, of the 400 respondents interviewed, 5.5 percent, or 30 people, said district commissioner very unprofessional, 19.9 percent or 80 respondents say unprofessional, 34.8 percent or 139 respondents said professional, 4.2 percent or 17 respondents say it is very professional, while 35.6 percent, or 142 people / respondents undecided. As for the question relating to the procurement of logistics and distribution of ballot papers, out of 400 respondents about the professionalism of the Election Commission of Regency in the procurement of logistics and distribution of ballot papers, 4.2 percent or 17 people who said district commissioner very unprofessional, 13.6 percent or 54 respondents said unprofessional, 42.6 percent or 170 respondents said professional, 5.5 percent or 22 respondents say it is very professional, while 34.2 percent, or 137 respondents undecided.

The next question related to the implementation of the campaign, 400 respondents were interviewed by 8.6 percent, or 45 people who said district commissioner / City very unprofessional, 16.7 percent or 67 respondents say unprofessional, 34.7 percent or 139 respondents said professional, or 4.7 percent 19 respondents said it was very professional, while 35.2 percent, or 141 people / respondents undecided. As for questions related to the socialization of the implementation of the presidential election, of the 400 respondents interviewed, 9.3 percent or 37 people who said district commissioner / City very unprofessional, 20.4 percent or 82 respondents say unprofessional, 30.7 percent or 123 respondents said professional, 4.4 percent or 16 respondents say it is very professional, while 35.1 percent, or 140 respondents undecided. Likewise, questions relating to the updating of the voters' data, of the 400 respondents interviewed, 10.1 percent, or 40 people who said district commissioner very unprofessional, 26 percent or 104 respondents said unprofessional, 23.1 percent or 92 respondents said professional, 3.4 percent or 13 respondents say it is very professional, while 37.4 percent, or 150 respondents undecided (Figure 9 and Table 1).

Conclusion

Still the poor responsiveness of the whole range of good organizers Bawaslu and the structure underneath, as well as Provincial KPU, Regency KPU, PPK, and RPM / KPPS in response to alleged violations of the code of conduct in the election is still relatively slightly. The still high public perception associated with respondents' doubts on the implementation of the 2014 presidential election, though others give a positive impression on the organizers of the 2014 presidential election. Improvements to the quality of selection and recruitment organizer strictly in order to reach the organizers credible and responsive in addressing the alleged violations of the code of conduct in the election is still relatively slightly. Voter education and political education in general that elections can participate in the 2014 presidential election. Avoiding Abstentions (Turnout Voter) by improving

the management of elections, the organizers were professional and has integrity, political education for awareness of participation choose smart and qualified, repair system pemutakhiran Data Selector, change the public's distrust of the organizers of the way the practice of transparency and accountability of the providers through dialogue, reports and audit

Recommendation

Ahead Election Commission and the Election Supervisory Agency of the provincial level to the district level need to improve integrity in the event; act in a neutral and impartial justice to all couples, not interfering with the other party, not partisan, on hearing all the parties, and not accept gifts of any kind. Responsiveness required a whole range of good organizers of election supervisory agency (Bawaslu) and the underlying structures, as well as provincial election commission (KPU) and underlying structures in response to alleged violations of the code of conduct in elections.

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